

QUALITY ASSURANCE OF MARINE STRUCTURES FOR YACHTS MADE ON ADVANCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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Materials and production procedures for building racing yachts are reviewed. Taking into account the lack of Rules and criteria for assuring quality of marine structures made in Advanced Composite Materials the quality philosophy followed by ASTILLEROS ESPAÑOLES is explained.

1. INTRODUCTION

Conventional composite materials -polyester reinforced with glass fibres in different forms: mats or roving- produced by wet lay-up method have been used for a long period of time in marine applications. All Classification Societies and some other Marine Institutions have stated rules and regulations in order to assess the final quality of boats and yachts.

But when other reinforcements, resins or production methods different from the conventional ones stated above are to be used, the situation changes. At the moment Classification Societies have no standard rules for this materials. If different materials from glass and polyester are used, plans are asked to be submitted to the Classification Society. Depending on the Society, if a complete certification is asked, some recommendations on process are obtained but the minimum scantlings are compulsory. And this last condition cannot be required for a racing yacht where weight and so scantlings have been optimized. Concerning production no indications for other processes as wet lay-up assisted with vacuum or high curing temperature prepregs with vacuum are given.

This paper summarizes the procedure followed by "Factoría de Puerto Real" of ASTILLEROS ESPAÑOLES in order to build racing yachts with a high quality standard

2. MATERIALS AND PRODUCTION PROCEDURES FOR BUILDING RACING YACHTS

2.1 Materials

The yacht structure may be considered as the one which provides the strength and stiffness to withstand all of the loads which the yacht may reasonably be expected to experience.

The strength of the yacht concerns its ability to withstand the loads imposed on it. Adequate strength without yielding in the case of metallic materials or matrix cracking when composite materials are used, is easy to provide if the loads are known and if excess weight is no objection.

The stiffness of a structure is its resistance to deflection under load within the elastic limit of the material. Stiffness is directly proportional to the modulus of elasticity of the material and the moment of inertia of the section, but varies inversely with the span. That means that yacht stiffness is the result of a combination of the scantlings, geometry and the material chosen for the hull girder.

Both criteria -strength and stiffness- must be taken into account in selecting the adequate material for a yacht, but when both are achieved, stiffness is that of primary concern. A high stiffness avoids hull deflection and allows a better knowledge of the rigging geometric characteristics and thus a higher aerohydrodynamic efficiency. (Belgrano , Riley and Honey).

When considering the design of racing yachts a third criteria have to be taken into account : weight. And minimum weight structures exhibiting maximum stiffness is the mandatory condition from the design point of view.

Comparing materials performance, the lightest hull girder for maximum stiffness will be obtained when advance composite materials are used (Parga, Sarabia) . And ranging the materials from this point of view the following is obtained: advanced composite materials -epoxy resin reinforced with carbon fibre, epoxy resin reinforced with kevlar, epoxy resin reinforced with glass-, polyester resin reinforced with unidirectional glass, aluminum, polyester resin reinforced with glass fibres in the form of roving or mats with glass content greater than 30%, steel and polyester reinforced with a low content of glass fibers. Summarizing, racing yachts should be made in Advanced Composite Materials.

2.2. Production Procedures

Composite Materials can be manufactured by a number of techniques which aim to combine the fiber and resin into a well consolidated product. The manufacturing technique selected depends upon the size and quality of the composite required. Yachts have been usually manufactured by hand lay-up techniques in which the resin is applied by brush to sheets of fiber, often in the form of woven cloth and the excess squeezed out with a roller. The resin then cures at ambient temperature. It is extremely difficult to obtain high quality laminates by this method and the laminate weight and thickness is difficult to control.

An improvement to this technique consist on applying vacuum. It allows to remove the air entrapped, bleed a bit of resin during curing process and homogenize laminate thickness.

If the resin is already combined with the reinforcing fibers in the form of a pre-preg material, weight laminate can be minimized and higher quality materials can be obtained but more complicated production techniques must be used. Prepreg materials for marine applications cure at temperatures above 60 °C. In this case the quality of the finished material depends on vacuum, the correct application of the heating cycle and the technique used to bleed off excess of resin.

Maximum properties and the best quality are obtained when prepreg materials are cured applying vacuum plus a compaction pressure and all the properties above can be fairly controlled, i.e.: when an autoclave is used. This production method is extremely expensive and taking into account the dimensions of autoclaves for aeronautical purposes it can be only used for a few classes of racing yachts.

As the main requirement that the Design Office ask for laminates is fibre volume fraction, it has been taken as criteria in order to compare the manufacturing methods applicable in shipyards. These are: wet lay-up without vacuum, wet lay-up with vacuum and prepreg materials of high curing temperature with vacuum. Data from manufacturer is shown in table 1(SPS).

It can be observed that the best mechanical properties are achieved when prepreg materials are used and vacuum is applied.

Manufacturing method	Fibre Volume Fraction %
wet lay-up without vacuum, cured at ambient temperature (reinforcement: Fabric)	33
wet lay-up without vacuum, cured at ambient temperature (reinforcement: Unidirectional)	36
wet lay-up with vacuum, cured at ambient temperature (reinforcement: Fabric)	40
wet lay-up without vacuum, cured at ambient temperature (reinforcement: Unidirectional)	43
Fabric reinforcement, prepreg, cured at 75°C with vacuum	46
Unidirectional reinforcement, prepreg, cured at 75°C with vacuum	50

Table 1: Fibre Volume Fraction (%) obtained by different manufacturing methods

3. ASTILLEROS ESPAÑOLES EXPERIENCE IN BUILDING RACING YACHTS

ASTILLEROS ESPAÑOLES entered the new market of Composite Materials Structures for racing yachts at the end of the eighties. It has built the Spanish America's Cup boats, and some other classes of yachts.

For a shipyard that uses to be a *materials user*, which buys materials that already contain all engineering properties, it is not easy to become a *materials producer*, where materials should undergo a chemical reaction before they achieve engineering properties, the structural quality is totally dependent on process and material properties are not tolerant of manufacturing errors. This asks for a big change of mind. But the shipyard has developed the proper techniques for building racing Yachts with Advanced Composite Materials and also Glass Reinforced Plastics.

The biggest yachts that have been produced in ASTILLEROS ESPAÑOLES Factoría de Puerto Real were the America's Cup Boats. They were made mainly in carbon fibre prepreg materials of 75° C curing temperature and applying vacuum. Other types of reinforcing fibres or hybrids have been also used for other projects.

4. ASTILLEROS ESPAÑOLES QUALITY CONTROL POLICY

When beginning an experienced team in building racing yachts formed by a boatbuilder and five laminators was hired in order to shorten our apprenticeship. No regulations nor acceptance or rejection criteria for marine structures manufactured in advanced composite materials were found. Classification Societies have no published rules for this materials. Design Offices asks for a minimum volume fraction or even nothing; drawings are presented specifying laminate lay-up and details, but nothing about minimum properties required. And they left all the responsibility and production requirements to the materials manufacturer, i.e.. the shipyard. Concerning the experts hired, a great sensibility about laminate weight were found, but not about defects.

There are many revisions on the effect of defects in Composite Materials for aerospace applications produced by autoclave technique (Bishop, Dorey). Standards for Quality have been widely developed and experienced and a complete Damage Tolerance approach has emerged. This is not the situation in Marine World as it has been told above.

Taking into account the atmosphaera outlined, ASTILLEROS ESPAÑOLES Development Branch decided to set its own Quality System on Advanced Composite Materials based in a Damage Tolerance Approach. In order to do that, the conclusions that are emerging for defect significance studies of Advanced Composite Materials for aerospace applications were studied, they served us as a general guide, several meetings with the materials manufacturer were organized and the types of failures occurred in racing yachts reported by sailors were also studied.

And as a consequence of that, a minimum defect policy was decided. The following defects were seen as being of primary importance:

- Voids
- Incorrect fiber volume fraction
- Incorrect curing
- Incorrect lay-up
- Delaminations
- Bonding defects

The presence of voids is one of the most important manufacturing defect. They maybe caused by several factors such us air entrapment, insufficient resin, excessive exothermic during curing, or porous molds. Its volume is important because of its influence on the interlaminar shear strength. And as no criteria is established by Classification Societies for Advanced Composite Materials the question of what defines a good-quality laminate void content, comes here. The ideal laminate should be free of all voids or porosity defects. In aerospace criteria depending on applications, generally less than 1% to 2% (Hinrich). Our objective has been to know our level and try to achieve the minimum.

Incorrect fiber volume fraction due to insufficient or excess of resin maybe caused by an incorrect storage, handling or processing of materials. It will usually be accompanied by voids as will incorrectly cured resin. It influences strength and stiffness. Our objective has been to get, at least, the one asked by the designer.

Delaminations or separation of the individual layers is probably the most serious defect and requires careful repair to maintain a structurally sound laminate. They may be caused by a number of reasons which include contaminated reinforcement, failure to clean surfaces during multistage lay-ups, excessive drilling pressure, forceful removal of a part from the mold, damage from sharp impacts, forcing a laminate into place during assembly, and excessive exothermic and shrinkage particularly in heavy sections (SNAME). As the interlaminar toughness of laminates is the lowest toughness, they seriously affect mechanical performance in compression. They also lower the laminate stiffness.(T.K.O'Brien).

Our objective has been free of delaminations. This is difficult to certify because most of them are only detected by ultrasonic techniques. The size of these produced by excessive drilling pressure can be approximately predicted by visual inspection, and here interlaminar toughness data are important in order to assess the loss of compressive strength because of delamination. The rest of them are not possible to detect unless special inspection techniques are used. But taking into account its sources we had many ways in order to minimize them.

Bonding defects are important in both bonded assemblies and bonding between skins and core in sandwich structures. Common defects are voids and debonding. These may be caused by poor fitting and alignment of the component parts, improper vacuum and surface contamination. Another difficulty is also added because there are no standard inspection methods for adhesive joints.

Taking into account our limitations, the quality control system was designed for avoiding those defects of primary importance and, if possible, any type of defect. In order to do that it was planned: A careful control of environment conditions and facilities, a correct treatment of materials in all stages of production, and personal training.

5. THE QUALITY ASSURANCE AND ITS IMPROVEMENTS

5.1 Raw Materials Reception

Raw Materials Reception Control is important for every material, but when prepreg materials are used it is vital. In this case temperature records are checked and a complete roll codification is to be made. Random Inspection concerning prepreg physicochemical characterization is run only if necessary.

5.2. Materials storage and handling.

In order to avoid dispersions of resin content and excess or insufficient resin areas caused because of gravity in prepregs rolls, several shelves have been installed inside the freezer and in the warm up area.

Temperature during storage was kept at 20°C below 0°C .Time exposure of any prepreg roll has been recorded.

In order to study the degradation rate of prepregs, resin reaction enthalpy were determined during first projects by Differential Scanning Calorimetry for prepregs that were hold during three days at 5°C. It was determined according I+D-E-241(CASA) with a heating rate of 10°C/min. Results are on table II.

Table II: Resin Reaction Enthalpy Ampreg 25/Carbon fiber

Sample	ΔH (J/g)	%Resin
1	243,3	39,8
2	257,9	41,0
Average	253,9	40,4

Typical values for these materials given by the materials manufacturer are between 290 and 340 J/g. That means that temperature during storage must be carefully controlled. Prepreg degradations can affect chemical reactivity, the formation of the polymer network and the increase of void content as time exposure increases.

Void content control follows with prepregs handling. Prepreg material was allowed to warm up to room temperature in the original sealed package and care was on the temperature of the prepreg: to be in excess of the dew point temperature before the backing films were removed to ensure that moisture does not condense on the materials.

Nomex and foams have been kept in a separate area near the oven. And prior to use Nomex core panels they have been completely dry.

5.3. Production environment

Factoría de Puerto Real is placed in the South of Spain and weather conditions are not good for Composite Materials manufacturing. It is humid, sometimes windy, and hot during almost six months per year. This weather conditions ask for a complete isolated and conditioned shipyard which have not been fully achieved yet.

In order to control dust, humidity and temperature during all the process the following facilities were installed:

- A freezer shop with temperature control and always at 20°C below 0° for storage.
- Air conditioning with humidity control and heating were installed for drying, refrigerating or warming the air. Outhblowers for dust and air
- A big oven with temperature control and thermocouple attachment . And a heater was also installed.
- Thermohygrometers.
- Vacuum system with several lines on the different working areas.

All the calibration process of equipment and systems were conducted by Lloyd's' Register of Shipping.

5.4. Workmanship

Skillness of laminators have been found of primary importance. Laminate quality is strongly dependent upon laminator skillness. At the beginning, an expert of the Spanish Aeronautical Company CASA moved to Cadiz during three days in order to teach our team about the correct handling of materials: cutting, layingup etc.

5.5. Production procedure

5.5.1. Tooling

In order to have a better accuracy in lines, frames were mechanized by autokon automatic cutting from the lines delivered by designers

As tooling are fabricated in wood, care is to be put in drying it to eliminate moisture content prior to build then. And as one of the reasons of vacuum leakage is the porosity of tooling, care is to be put on sealing and airtighten them.

Base plate flatness has also been controlled with laser.

5.5.2. Lay-up .

Mechanical properties strongly depends on lay-up. So lay-up procedures must be consistent with the drawings for orientation. Lay-up sequence was controlled by the master and in some projects by Classification Societies Inspectors.

5.5.3. Vacuum control

After the lay-up is finished bagging and the vacuum level and its uniformity in several places is to be inspected.

Vacuum strongly affects void content. During trials for one of the first projects, vacuum was expected to be 95% . We only achieved 70%-85% and it was not uniform. All the vacuum system was checked. Some leakages on lines were detected. They were repaired but the desired vacuum was not achieved. In order to analyze vacuum influence on final quality, several tests were run. The following physical properties for laminates produced with wet lay-up and with and without vacuum were obtained: Density, Fiber volume fraction, Resin volume fraction and Void volume

Physical properties for a laminate of 3.7 mm average thickness, which consisted on several layers of carbon biaxial reinforcement were measured. It was produced by wet lay-up without vacuum and cured at ambient temperature. It showed big dispersions on fiber volume fractions and void content. Specimens were obtained from different parts of the laminate in order to study fiber volume gradients. For that laminate void content volume varied between 9% and 14% and fiber volume fraction between 36% and 48%.

Fibre volume fractions of a similar laminate manufactured by an expert laminator, cured at ambient temperature and at 30 KPa pressure was 48,30 % and void content was 4.30 %. No important gradients were found. But it was found to be dependent on laminators skillness and panel size. It was decided to change vacuum pumps

Void content is varying nowadays between 2.7% and 4.2% for inner hull and outer hull laminates when curing large surfaces. Fiber volume fraction has increased to the interval 54% and 52% for the same laminates.

5.5.4. Curing

Curing process is monitored by using at least four thermocouples installed in the zones that have been identified as coldest zones.

Mechanical properties for cured laminates (Tensile strength, Tensile modulus and Interlaminar shear strength) are obtained and have been compared for the three production systems used in different parts of Yachts. Important increases in Interlaminar shear strength have been obtained when decreasing void content. Low Interlaminar shear strength values are obtained when biaxial fabrics are used.(Parga, Sarabia)

5.5.5.Assembling.

To be mentioned again the great difficulty in getting the workers from the shipyard and the boatbuilders conscious about delaminations and the proper way of assembling.

For the carbon fibre materials used in some projects, GJC data from manufacturer was 205.9 Jm^{-2} for Ampreg 75 . The GJC value for Ampreg 25 was 117.5 Jm^{-2} .It has been found (Parga, Sarabia) that laminates with delaminations of 5 cm diameter , exhibit residual compressive strength ratios of approximately 0.3. That size of delamination was produced at the beggining by no skilled workers. In order to avoid that situation the expert from CASA was asked to train our people in drilling carbon fiber and special care was put on this operation. An important improvement was observed.

6. CONCLUSIONS

1. A great effort has been done by ASTILLEROS ESPAÑOLES in order to minimize defects in Composite Materials Structures.
- 2.The quality level achieved is high. Composite Material Structures with void content between 2.7% and 4.2% are produced. Laminators skillness and controlled facilities have been found of primary importance
- 3.More research is needed in marine applications of Composite Materials in order to set acceptance or rejection criteria.

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